

Experimental Psychophysical Characterization and Validation of Sound Exciter Vibrotactile Actuators in Haptics

Alessia Sivia Ivani^{§1 2 3}, Manuel G. Catalano¹, Simone Fani³, Giorgio Grioli^{1 2}, Antonio Bicchi^{1 2}

Abstract—Vibrotactile actuators, such as voice coils, are effective, non-invasive solutions commonly used in haptics to render tactile information. Among voice coils, sound exciters offer several advantages to wearable haptics through superior economic affordability, compact size, and commercial availability. This study explores the feasibility of using disk-shaped sound exciters actuators for wearable haptic applications, bench-marking them against traditional voice coil cylindrical actuators. Seven participants took part in contact and roughness discrimination experiments. The qualitative and quantitative study investigates the Just Noticeable Difference (JND) and Absolute Threshold (AT), exploiting standard psychophysical methods. The proposed protocol effectively compared the performance of the two actuators. Our preliminary results show that sound exciters may be a viable alternative to more commonly used vibrotactile actuators for practical haptic applications.

I. INTRODUCTION

Among non-invasive tactile feedback, vibrotactile stimulation is one of the most studied techniques due to the ease of tactile modulation w.r.t. other approaches involving, for instance, static pressure or skin stretch [1]. Vibrotactile devices find application in many fields such as telerobotics, virtual reality, robot-assisted surgical tasks, or prosthetic areas [2]–[4]. Voice coils vibrotactile actuators have been preferred solutions to other actuators because of their relevant features: fast dynamic response and maximum force/mass ratio [1], [5]. Indeed, in our previous work [6], a generic voice coil actuator without bushing (NCC01-04-001-1) by H2W Technologies was used to transmit vibrotactile stimuli to the users' skin. Despite their wide applications, the affordability and accessibility of generic voice coil linear actuators are questionable, with prices of the order of magnitude of hundreds of dollars. Moreover, traditional cylindrical shape of generic voice coil and their cases, developed in height, complicates wearability.

Since the mechanical frequency vibration of vibrotactile devices, in the range 60-1000 Hz, matches with the audio frequency range, even adapted voice coil sound exciters have been used to provide vibrotactile feedback information and/or to support music experience [7]–[9]. Sound exciter prices, almost two orders of magnitude lower than traditional

Fig. 1: Voice coil cylindrical actuator (left) and disk-shaped sound exciter (right) comparison.

voice coil actuators, and their compact shape developed in width, make them a potentially valid alternative to conventional voice coil actuators for wearable and accessible to all haptic feedback devices. To the best of our knowledge, qualitative and quantitative comparison between bench-mark voice coil vibrotactile actuators and sound exciters actuators is missing.

The aim of this work is to qualitative and quantitatively test the effectiveness of the Disk-shaped Actuator (DA) of the sound exciter type (DAEX13CT-4 Coin Type Exciter, by Dayton Audio) in conveying vibrotactile feedback cues by comparison with the voice coil Cylindrical Actuator (CA) (NCC01-04-001-1 by H2W Technologies) (Fig. 1). Our ultimate goal is to find an accessible and valid haptic feedback solution that is easy to use, implement and integrate to improve prosthesis acceptance and daily use for amputees.

II. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

We performed a psychophysical characterization of the system in terms of Just Noticeable Difference (JND) and Absolute Threshold (AT). Two separate experiments have been carried out. In each experiment, both actuators were tested. Seven healthy participants (age mean \pm SD: 26.6 \pm 2.05) were enrolled and asked to give their informed consent to participate to both experiments.

To test the capacity of human participants to detect a tactile contact cue rendered by the actuators, we performed the *Contact Discrimination Experiment* with the method of limits. Signals were artificially reproduced and recorded from the index finger of a Pisa/IIT SoftHand device [6], hereinafter SoftHand, during an impact with a pendulum. Descending and ascending series of stimuli were presented to participants who indicated whether the stimulus was perceived or not. The overall AT for each actuator was computed as the mean of the AT for each participant.

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¹with Soft Robotics for Human Cooperation and Rehabilitation, Istituto Italiano di Tecnologia, Genova 16163, Italy.

²with Centro di ricerca E. Piaggio, University of Pisa, Pisa 56122, Italy.

³with Department of Information Engineering, University of Pisa, Pisa 56122, Italy.

[§] Corresponding author alessia.ivani@iit.it

Fig. 2: Absolute Thresholds: outliers (red crosses) and median values (red lines) of subjects' ATs.

Fig. 3: Just Noticeable Difference: GLMM fitting for all subjects for CA and DA actuators.

For roughness discrimination, we used the method of constant stimuli and performed the *Roughness Discrimination Experiment*. The experiment evaluated the capacity of human participants to discriminate different levels of roughness rendered by the actuators, corresponding to different sandpaper grit signals. Again signals were artificially reproduced through the SoftHand. Couples of stimuli were presented to participants, who were asked to report which of the two felt rougher. With a Generalized Linear Mixed Model (GLMM), we tested whether the actuator type affected the perceived roughness and we estimated the JNDs as in [10].

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

For the *Contact Discrimination Experiment*, the overall AT for the DA and the CA were 0.28 ± 0.05 N, 0.31 ± 0.09 respectively. A T-test revealed no significant effect between the two actuators with a p-value $p > 0.05$. Fig. 2 shows outliers and median values of AT for each actuator. For the *Roughness Discrimination Experiment*, the slope of the overall model, considering the answers of both actuators, was positive highlighting that subjects were able to discriminate between stimuli. Considering separately DA and CA actuators contribution to the model (Fig.3), the slopes of the curves were not significantly different from the overall model with a $p > 0.05$, highlighting that the use of a different type of actuator did not affect the response. Accordingly, JND was equal to $82.79 \mu\text{m}$ for the DA and $70.96 \mu\text{m}$ for the CA.

IV. DISCUSSION

From the *Contact Discrimination Experiment*, all participants were able to detect stimuli with both actuators with overlapping Absolute Thresholds. The two actuators' effectiveness in transmitting vibrotactile contact cues is

comparable. In the *Roughness Discrimination Experiment* revealed consistent behaviors when discriminating roughness stimuli with the two actuators. DA JND was comparable with the CA actuator, and their use did not significantly affect the subjects' responses. Without lateral motion, the passive exploration of stimuli by the subjects in our experiment could have negatively affected the overall JND results. A reduction in performance was also expected, considering that signals were recorded from a robotic hand exploration of rough surfaces. Moreover, participants were novel in experiencing roughness-related cues.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we successfully tested the effectiveness of the disk-shaped actuator, a sound exciter, in conveying vibrotactile cues and in rendering roughness of surfaces when explored by a robotic hand. The psychophysical analysis allowed a quantitative comparison with the bench-marked cylindrical actuator. The preliminary results of the two psychophysical experiments demonstrated that sound exciters' performances are comparable to generic voice coil actuators for vibrotactile rendering. Future works will focus on increasing the number of subjects and integrating the actuators in prosthetic sockets. Considering sound exciter compact shape and affordability, they may be a viable alternative to more commonly used vibrotactile actuators for practical haptic applications.

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